

Electronic - Human Resource Management: Opportunities and Challenges in LED Lighting Industry

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Abstract:- The researcher aims to study E-HRM: Opportunities and challenges The opportunities and challenges of electronic human resource management, the information that has been studied to find ways to prepare personnel in the human resource department of the company. This research examines the concepts and experimental facts by collecting the information that needs to be collected from specific secondary data sources such as research papers, newspaper articles, and electronic resources on electronic human resource management. Various in Thailand and abroad, this research study The researcher has formulated a conceptual framework from the synthesis of concepts, theories, and research related to electronic human resource management based on the concept ., Ruel, Huub; Bondarouk, Tanya; Looise, Jan Kees(2004) John W. Boudreau (1991), M.Voermans(2007), Sucheta Agarwal (2018)., E-HRM: Innovation or irritation. An explorative empirical study in five large Companies on web-based HRM., Using Performance Measurement to Evaluate Strategic Human Resource Management Decisions: Kodak's Experience With Profit Sharing. Profit-sharing is frequently used to link employee performance and labor costs to the profitability of organizations., The most commitment of the show think about has been to shed light on how dialect standardization influences client acknowledgment and utilize of IT, in this case, e-HRM frameworks. It too speaks to one of few experimental thinks about to explore e-HRM in an MNC setting., An attitude towards E-HRM: an empirical study at Philips. Nowadays, companies seek possibilities to run HR operations more efficiently., and Managing Organization Effectiveness through E-Human Resource Management Tool-E-Learning: INDIAN Cases a Qualitative Approach. Continuity and social norms with analysis and analysis of inferential statistics (Inferential Statistics) is the analysis of structural equation modeling (Structural Equation Modeling: SEM). The results showed The way a company manages its employees affects how dedicated the employees are in the light industry. Hypothesis 1(H₁) Causal Model of Human Resource Management Influences on Organizational Engagement of Employees in Light Industry DE=0.418* Accepted and Hypothesis 1(H₂) Management Model Development Human resources influence the organizational commitment of employees in LED Lighting Industry. with influencing standards. DE=0.342*,IE=0.247*Accept.

Keywords:- Electronic Human Resource Management (E-HRM), Opportunities, Electronic Human Resource Management Activities.

I. INTRODUCTION

E-HRM, the utilize of web-based advances for human asset administration hones and arrangements, is developing inside organizational life. Much is claimed and communicated around the preferences of e-HRM, but logical confirmation of these focal points is rare. There's no clear prove to reply the address of whether e-HRM contributes to HRM viability and "e-HRM hardly helped to improve employee competencies" [1]. Ruel, Huub; Bondarouk, Tanya; Looise, Jan Kees(2004) CONSULTANCY FIRMS, INSTEAD OF ACADEMICS, HAVE BEEN BEHIND THE PRIMARY ENDEAVORS TO EXAMINE WHETHER THE ENDEAVORS PUT INTO THE E-HRM LEAD TO THE ANTICIPATED RESULTS, BUT THESE EVALUATIONS TEND TO HAVE A NON-OBJECTIVE DISCUSS. "Presents utility analysis, a family of theories and measures designed to describe, predict" [2] BOUDREAU, J. W. (1991).UTILITY INVESTIGATION FOR CHOICES IN HUMAN ASSET MANAGEMENT.IN M. D. DUNNETTE & L. M. HOUGH (EDS.), HANDBOOK OF MECHANICAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL BRAIN RESEARCH (PP. 621-745). "More and more organizations have been replacing face-to-face human RESOURCE MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES" [3]Voermans, M. and van Veldhoven, M.J.P.M. (2007) The Part of Electronic Human Asset Administration IN Modern HUMAN Asset Administration. OPEN Diary OF SOCIAL SCIENCES Vol.3 No.4, April 2015. THE Inclusion OF The scholarly community IN THIS Subject IS MORE Later AND HAS NOT However Driven TO Genuine ANSWERS. OF E-HRM IS CERTAINLY NOT Getting to be Out of date, AND ITS FULL POTENTIAL IS STILL Expected, Subsequently Scholarly Association Within The Point Has To Develop. IN THIS ARTICLE, WE PRESENT THE RESULTS OF A QUANTITATIVE STUDY ON THE QUESTION OF WHETHER E-HRM CONTRIBUTES TO HRM EFFECTIVENESS. FOR THIS PURPOSE, WE MEASURED THE ASSESSMENT OF E-HRM APPLICATIONS, DEFINED AS THE EXTENT TO WHICH E-HRM APPLICATIONS ARE PERCEIVED AS APPROPRIATE FOR THEIR USE, AND THE EXTENT TO WHICH EMPLOYEES PERCEIVED THE RESULTING HRM TO BE EFFECTIVE, USING A STRATIFIED SAMPLE. THIS WAS CARRIED OUT IN A LARGE GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATION: THE DUTCH MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS. THE ARTICLE IS ORGANIZED AS TAKES AFTER: TO BEGIN WITH, WE SUMMARIZE IMPROVEMENTS IN INQUIRE ABOUT ON E-HRM AND "HUMAN RESOURCE PLANNING" [4] Groe, G. M., PYLE, W., JAMROG, J. J. (1996).

Information technology and HR. Human Resource Planning, 19(1), 56–61. HRM EFFECTIVENESS, AND THEN WE CONCENTRATE ON OUR PARTICULAR WAY OF THINKING, SHOW THE PLAN FOR RESEARCH, AND EXPLAIN THE RESEARCH METHOD. THIS IS FOLLOWED BY THE PRESENTATION OF THE RESULTS. THE ARTICLE FINISHES WITH CONCLUSIONS AND A DISCUSSION.

II. E-HRM

A. *Electronic Human Resource Management (E-HRM)*

First, is a company process that combines HR departments with data innovation particularly outlined to help with errands related to human assets. By doing so, businesses can progress their human assets or HR offices and be more proficient in terms of both fetched and efficiency. The errands that E-HRM can handle incorporate staffing, preparing, and finance. Computer program is introduced that can handle numerous time-consuming errands, sparing HR staff time on those assignments and centering on key arranging outlined to make strides the trade. It is basic to companies around the world. These divisions are mindful for communication between administration and workers. Their endeavors can apparently make the distinction between a bunch of fulfilled laborers and a gather of workers who are disappointed. Taking care to meet the assorted needs of workers can be troublesome when all the specialized errands of HR administration are. must be done as well This can be why numerous companies have begun the method of actualizing electronic human asset administration to assist their HR supervisors. (Netinbag.com)

It is important to understand that in most cases E-HRM

This doesn't take the place of regular HR departments. Instead, it's seen as a supporting role for HR, which could hold back HR from doing important strategic tasks. If companies use e-HRM software, they can make the HR department work more smoothly by doing complex tasks more easily. Electronic human resource management is when computer programs are used to help with tasks related to employee payment, which used to be handled by the HR department. "Using e-HRM can help manage employee benefits." The software is useful for managing staff. Special software that sorts job applications or recommends candidates from within the company can take a long time to select from all the choices. But these programs make it easier to find suitable job candidates. Electronic Human Asset Administration can offer assistance HR offices center on building good relationships between management and employees. E-HRM can make it easier for the HR department to talk with employees by using a special website that connects them. E-HRM helps HR employees focus on important projects that can make the company better.

III. ACTIVITIES E-HRM

"The courageous unused world of HR: Human assets administration within the advanced age" [5] Guetal, H. G., Stone, D. L. (Eds.). (2005). The brave new world of HR: Human resources management in the digital age. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass. You need to know that usually E-HRM does not take the place of regular human resources departments. Using E-HRM can make it easier to manage employee benefits. When companies use software to sort through job applications or recommend internal candidates for job openings, it can take a long time to decide which person to hire. However, this makes it easier for the company to manage the hiring process because there are many options to choose from.

A. *e-Recruitment*

"The way leaders lead can impact how workers come up with new ideas." [6] Krisada Chienwattanasook (2019). Working Environment and Motivation Affecting Team Performance: Empirical Data from a Computer Equipment Manufacturing Company. Academic Journal Bangkokthonburi University Vol.8 No.2 July-December 2019 P.219-230. Moreover known as online enlisting, is being broadly utilized by companies these days. Through e-Recruitment, companies as a rule contract candidates utilizing the Web as a medium. The common hone of encouraging online enlistment is by uploading the enrollment data on the company's official site or enlisting online enrollment websites to serve the reason. Monster.com, Naukri.com, and Timesjob.com are a few of the well-renowned online enrollment websites.

B. *e-Selection*

The HR office utilizing the online determination handle must guarantee that each step complies with the procedural necessities viz. Venture steps, seller choice, appraisal steps, criticism to the candidates, etc. The reason of E-selection The goal is to use more people while spending less money and taking less time.

C. *E-Performance Administration*

Lots of businesses use online tools to check how well someone is doing their job. There are two ways to check how someone is working. One is to use a tool on the computer that records everything they do. The other way is to write reviews and give feedback on a website.

D. *E-Learning*

This means using the internet or the company's private network to do something. Make it easier for employees to learn and grow through training and development. By using online training, it's possible to train a lot of employees no matter where they are.

E. *E-Remuneration*

An organization utilizing remuneration administration online empowers to accumulate, store, analyze, and disseminate emolument information or data to anybody at any time. Moreover, the person can get to electronically dispersed stipend computer program, and expository apparatuses, from any put within the world.

Fig. 1: Activities of E-HRM
Fig. 1: Activities E-HRM

IV. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- Opportunities and challenges of electronic human resource management in the LED Lighting Industry in Thailand.
- R To bring information that has been studied to find ways to prepare personnel in the human resources department of the company in Thailand.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher has formulated a conceptual framework from the synthesis of concepts, theories, and research related to electronic human resource management based on the concept., Activities E-HRM, E-HRM: Innovation or irritation.

By collecting data from 385 employees in the light industry. And use the questionnaire as a tool Statistics used in data analysis were descriptive statistics consisting of frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Causes of Human Asset Administration in Enrollment and Choice Preparing and Advancement execution examination Recompense and benefits on the organizational commitment of representatives in the light industry the various aspects are the feeling aspect. Continuity and social norms with analysis and analysis of inferential statistics (Inferential Statistics) is the analysis of structural equation modeling (Structural Equation Modeling: SEM).

VI. RESULTS

Table 1: Summary table of research hypothesis testing results

<i>Hypothesis Research</i>	<i>Influence</i>	<i>Accept/Reject</i>
Hypothesis 1 (H₁) The way a company manages its employees affects how dedicated the employees are in the light industry.	DE=0.418*	Accept
Hypothesis 2 (H₂) Human Resource Management Model Development Influences on Organizational Engagement of Employees in Standardized Light Industry	DE=0.342*, IE=0.247*	Accept

The causal relationship demonstrate of human asset administration to the organizational commitment of workers.in LED Lighting Industry. Hypothesis 1(H₁) The way a company manages its employees affects how dedicated the employees are in the light industry. DE=0.418* Accepted and Hypothesis 1(H₂) Management Model Development Human resources influence the organizational commitment of employees in the LED Lighting Industry. With influencing standards. DE=0.342*,IE=0.247*Accept.

a salary increase. Performance assessment results can be used as a basis for a reasonable pay increase. Including being an important indicator for considering annual bonuses as well which can help to motivate to work and increase the effectiveness of work.

VII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The results were discovered in this study.

- Training and Development On the learner side, learning and skills required in the current job in the organization can be developed with qualified personnel. Being knowledgeable and therefore able to create quality work for the organization will gain a reputation and more profitable.
- Performance appraisal Salary increases and bonus payments based on salary performance are important to all employees. And one of the career advancements is being considered for

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The causal relationship model of human resource management to the organizational commitment of employees. in LED Lighting Industry. Hypothesis 1(H₁) The way a company manages its employees affects how dedicated the employees are in the light industry. DE=0.418* Accepted and Hypothesis 1(H₂) Management Model Development Human resources influence the organizational commitment of employees in the LED Lighting Industry. With influencing standards. DE=0.342*,IE=0.247*Accept.

- Inferential Statistics is the analysis of structural equation modeling (Structural Equation Modeling: SEM).

chi-square=\cmin, df=\df, chi-square/df=\cmindf, P-value=\p,
 RMSEA=\rmsea, CFI=\cfi, TLI=\tli, GFI=\gfi, AGFI=\agfi,
 RMR=\rmr, HOELTER=\hfive (1)

Fig. 2: Structural Equation Modeling: SEM

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